

DIDACTIC PROVISION OF THE USE OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE COMPETENCE OF MANAGEMENT PERSONNEL IN THE SPHERE OF DIGITIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article provides detailed information on the development of educational policies and strategies, the introduction of a new reporting mechanism in the educational system, the implementation of educational strategies for sustainable development, as well as projects of international organizations, the preparation of strategic documents, reports, reform projects based on the results of analyzes and analyzes.*

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By the present time, the concept of "digital culture" becomes the subject of scientific and methodological considerations. The problem of the "civilization" of digitization and its global consequences remain relevant in the context of the modernization of educational processes. Digital Culture in higher education creates the need to update the principles and methods of work aimed at a digital age specialist in the future. The material level of digital culture - the object of analysis in it - is directly digital devices in all existing varieties. "Digital culture is a particular form of human being based on the creation of digital objects and phenomena that bring change to behavioral guidelines in traditional socio-cultural communications, it also includes digital literacy as one of the key elements of supporting certain values of a mentally reinforced person as well as creating a successful adaptation of a person to the digital environment. At the same time, digital culture is today a component of the general culture and is aimed at ensuring the information needs of humanity." [1]

The concept of "digital culture" was introduced into scientific circulation in the 2000s in connection with the emergence of the second generation technology of Web 2 Internet network services. The category of digital culture is primarily analyzed as a humanitarian, technological phenomenon in modern scientific literature. In modern science, scientists consider digital culture to be a technological phenomenon, since all objects of this culture work on the principle of digital coding of information with binary code using digital devices, and this culture becomes a system-generating factor. Thus, in order for the younger generation to successfully adapt to the digital environment, it is necessary not only to train, prepare for the correct acquisition of digital literacy skills, but also to form a digital culture in them. To do this, it is necessary to build educational activities saturated with information and communicative and value-specific aspects, the skills and qualifications acquired in the process of its implementation serve to solve practical tasks for both young people and the entire Uzbek people. [2]

Today, digital technologies are opening up wide opportunities for us and we recognize that they have great prospects in the field of Education. Modern teachers resort to the use of various

digital educational technologies in addition to parallel traditional classroom activities when conducting their classes: electronic textbooks, digital educational resources, Internet technologies, computer test programs, etc. Also, modern teachers are preparing with distance education, e-learning, public open online courses, open educational resources. Therefore, it is important to form a digital culture of future professionals, which is considered the driving force of the digital economy. So, since information technology covers all aspects of life, today "Digital Culture" is necessary for all professionals operating in both the technical and humanitarian spheres. "Digital culture" is a whole concept of the most basic modern communication technologies, the correct use of their functions in work or everyday life. A modern specialist with skills in the direction of "digital culture" knows how to properly use the tools that modern information and communication and digital technologies are offering, regardless of whether he specializes in the IT field or not.

Seven attributes of Digital Culture.

Digital culture can be based on unique features such as yega and a culture adapted only to change. In other cases, the Digital Transformation runs the risk of becoming the next set of documents for collecting iron dust in the warehouse. Thus, here are seven attributes of Digital Culture:

1-our organizational structure, processes, operational business model, culture – our IT systems and platforms.

Digital transformation is the movement to a digital organization, automated processes that require human participation in individual cases. In this regard, we do not rely on the organizational structure created "for someone", the processes and rituals established before the digital experience "you need to come here in person and personally bring all emails, orders and documents in printed form."

2-that all employees and managers are prepared for the fact that everything can change (from the business model to the role structure and the role of everyone).

Some departments are digitized, others eat outside the digital age, it is difficult to imagine an organization that performs its functions by entering information on paper or by hand. Digital transformation includes all sections, regardless of the role. In organizations, zones can exist without change, as a rule, they are created for "especially close" leaders. In such a distinctly non-digital culture, transformational changes and transition to fully digital processes are impossible.

3-complete openness to the outside world.

One of the distinguishing features of digital solutions is the ability to quickly cross borders and immediately conquer territories. Citizens of dozens of countries trade with each other on Chinese and American e-commerce platforms. Competition on online movie platforms is also global. Various options can be added to this attribute. You will connect to the external yegotizim of digital platforms, and yehtimol will create and market your own yechim. In digital culture, there is no place for the syndrome "not created by us", we constantly observe the world, Study, Act, borrow;

4-to operate in decision-making based on digital information rather than personal emotions.

The criterion of a digital organization is the acceptance of solving many issues without human participation. Artificial intelligence, big data and enterprise Automated Decision Systems based on the criteria currently needed, such as the decision to issue a loan on China's WeBank, will take about 10 seconds and will be based on real-time analysis of all digital traces of the borrower, including taking into account the amount automatically available due to the

characteristics of the borrower. If the digital platform is yega to each stage of the digital footprint (transaction volume, creditworthiness debts, income, etc.), who needs to go to the office to get a loan. As a result: in digital organization and Digital Culture, the activity and contribution of each person is seen digitized, transparent, objectively.

5-the speed of processes and decision-making tends to zero (the ability to accelerate all cycles to zero and seconds is the task and the norm). At the initial stage, proposals for digital optimization in the mode "5 days instead of 10" or "2 days instead of 3" are inevitable. Of course, this is progress, but it is far from digital thinking: How can we provide this service in seconds or minutes, what information do we have and what else should be included in the automatic decision cycle?

6-thinking on an infinite horizontal scale (the sky is not the limit)

Digital services can be delivered to consumers across a wider geographic area than a "corner office". If the physical reception of the service (e.g. carsharing) is related to the physical presence of the service facility, then access to the application can be provided from any part of the city by certain criteria. You can go even further: the WhasApp, Dodo Pizza and the same WeBank teams are made up of dozens, if not hundreds, of employees serving tens of millions of customers around the world.

7-customer oriented.

The ability to solve problems and prioritize customer needs in the design of digital services helps to create services that are really in demand. It is important to design a digital process in such a way that it not only meets the customer's expectations in terms of service speed and quality, but also exceeds it.

Recommendations for the development of Digital Culture:

1. Increase digital literacy (the study and use of digital tools).
2. Creating and promoting zones of digital experiments and new technologies, sharing success stories and positive emotions.
3. Create a place in your teams that cannot be punished: discuss mistakes not from the point of view of the guilty, but in the paradigm "what we can learn" (it is imperative to apply it in practice further).
4. Similar to other organizations that use digital technology to generate interest in it show Russian and world examples of problem solving: video clips, interactive, specific examples with numbers.
5. Moving in small systematic steps, showing success and results (PR projects should not replace successes, but silence is a mistake).

The digital maturity indicator is the achievement of a certain level of digital literacy. It is clear that digital organizations operate more dynamically than traditional organizations. From a practical point of view, digital culture establishes specific rules of Conduct for employees, creating a favorable environment for objective analysis and ground-based reasoning, giving employees a sense of determination and responsibility for making decisions on the spot. The sign of high Digital Culture and digital maturity of enterprises is to see and understand the context of digital transformation. For them, the high intensity of data flow, the rational organization of data arrays (Big Data), corporate and personal digital culture are more characteristic. Therefore, in the context of digital transformation, it is necessary to develop a new value system in terms of the interaction

of people and communities, as well as mutual understanding between specialists and managers, the creation of effective digital systems and communities for interaction in the field.

According to modern approaches, educational institutions should have such a pedagogical system that it is able to create the maximum conditions for the maturation of a person, the formation of inclinations, interests and abilities, as well as for his upbringing as a morally and morally worthy citizen. The advanced management system should ensure the proper functioning of the educational institution, as well as its continuous development, reconstruction and modernization in accordance with the direction of Community Renewal and social progress. That is, in the effective management of an educational institution, it should be considered important not only to navigate to the predicted results, but also to ensure the dynamics of its development.

Management culture as one of the main components of pedagogical culture increases management efficiency, improves quality indicators, plays a decisive role in establishing mutual responsibility and relationships between the participants of the managed system and the manager.

The management culture of the head of an educational institution is one of the important indicators in the formation of his personality, his acceptance as a yetakchi in school management and in other areas.[3] the analysis of the possibilities of the concepts of management culture and ability and the main indicators of their internal structure shows that these are an interactive concept in management, a set of business, professional and personal qualities of a leader for the successful performance of management and management tasks. The analysis of the state of management of educational institutions in meioria, high professionalism from its head and management of educational institutions in addition to organization shows that at present, the management culture of the leader, his ability to receive innovations lag behind changes in the development of pedagogical personnel and educational institutions.

In order to earn on educational achievements established on the basis of the goals of the educational system, the main tasks of management should be as follows:

- application of anti-centralization methods based on democratic principles;
- scheduled assessment and monitoring from time to time;
- to support the positive initiatives of educators and create conditions for them to receive the necessary information;
- creating conditions for improving the qualification level and improving professional skills (competence) of the teacher;
- ensuring that students are surrounded by an effective educational process;
- strengthening the activities of the board on management in order to democratize the education system and ensure the active participation of parents and students, in addition to teachers and representatives of the public, in its management.

In order to successfully manage the specified areas of activity, school leaders must have the following characteristics:

- ready to cooperate closely with employees in the team, he is well versed in the scientific foundations and methods of management, is aware of the science of conflict science, is able to make the right decisions in conflict situations;
- he tries to get to the goal, he is persistent, businessman and optimist, able to bring to the end what he started;
- is highly demanding of himself and his subordinates, receives criticism and self-criticism correctly;

- mastered the basics of personal discipline and executive culture and using them in their activities;

- restrained, fair, cautious and polite, devouring tolerance, sensitivity and exactingness in relations with colleagues and employees;

-highly civilized and simple in personal behavior.

Among the tasks of the relevant areas are the creation and implementation of a new management model in the educational system, a system of reporting and decision-making, setting priorities for Personnel Management and increasing the level of professional skill, while creating and implementing a new system of Management in the educational system.

The head of the educational institution must be a psychologist of his duties and duties. He must develop self-control in conflict situations, approach the emotional situation with humor, freely direct the interlocutor's attention in the direction he wants, enjoy his work and try to create conditions for his satisfaction with his work.

The optimized, managerial thinking of an educational institution, the level of fulfillment of educational goals and the recorded features of the qualitative Organization of management require him to always be careful in his work, develop the ability to analytically approach, be able to analyze and analyze his capabilities. self-adequate assessment at the level of resources and self-development. All this makes it possible to minimize the mistakes made when making management decisions, opens up wide opportunities for the formation of a qualitative, cost-effective personnel training process.

The main tasks of personnel planning and management directions are to determine the strategy of the Ministry of Education, prepare proposals for the formation of State Educational Policy and priorities, analyze information on the scale and effectiveness of the educational system, prepare strategic and annual plans of measures of the ministry, all structural divisions of the educational system and educational institutions, in the process of its preparation, ; regulation of work in the areas of further education, implementation of organizational and methodological guidance by educational management bodies and educational institutions on the implementation of current legislation related to the relevant areas.

Development of educational policies and strategies, introduction of a new reporting mechanism in the educational system, implementation of educational strategies for sustainable development, as well as projects of international organizations, preparation of strategic documents, reports, reform projects based on the results of analyzes and analyzes; development of proposals for improving the efficiency of general activities is carried out.

In the context of the Basic Rules of management theory, the following approaches should be used to assess the results of the activities of the pedagogical system and educational institution: the tasks of preparing reform projects and making proposals to improve the effectiveness of general activities are performed.[4] in the context of the Basic Rules of management theory, the following approaches should be used to assess the results of the activities of the pedagogical system and educational institution: the tasks of preparing reform projects and making proposals to improve the efficiency of general activities are carried out. In the context of the Basic Rules of management theory, the following approaches should be used to assess the results of the activities of the pedagogical system and educational institution:

development of criteria for determining the degree of efficiency of the process;

consider possible ways of working and choose effective methods of work sleeve;

taking into account all the circumstances that are expected and can change randomly; keeping in mind the factors that intentionally or accidentally oppose the work of the object and subjects under study.

One of the important criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of an educational institution is to determine its main goals. To do this, it is necessary to know what role the educational institution plays in the modern stage of development of society, what important tasks it performs. The main goal of the educational process in an educational institution should be the development of the personality of the student, while ensuring the acquisition of knowledge, skills and habits. In this work, mainly knowledge, skills and habits should play the role of tools.

The development of the student's personality includes high moral behavior, universal culture, creative initiative and business, communalism, maturation, etc. such characteristics mean upbringing.

The second group of important criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of an educational institution is the level of formation of a system of knowledge, skills and habits in students, the effectiveness of the educational process, the level of education, status of students. individual regions, processes and situation should be regularly evaluated on the basis of pre-prepared parameters and appropriate measures should be taken after summarizing the results.

T.I. Shamova, describing the professional competence of the head of the educational institution, expands the list of knowledge and requirements: she must have a complex of scientific knowledge and skills of a professional nature. In addition, T.I. Shamova emphasizes that this is knowledge of the latest achievements in the field of psychology, pedagogy, management theory, law, sociology, School Hygiene; this is the creative use of knowledge, respect for other people's opinions and the ability to conduct dialogue, discussion politely and reliably.[5]

Based on the analysis of the above points, it can be concluded that in the second group, the content of the concept of "professional competence of the head of an educational institution" is considered from the point of view of the activity approach, since its main characteristic is activity for the implementation of certain functions. The opinions of both groups of scientists are of a common nature yega, since this content of the concept indicates that it belongs to the profession of the manager and is his professional and personal characteristic.

It can be understood as the ability and preparation of the leader to identify, correctly formulate, make a holistic and in-depth analysis of the problems of the educational institution and find appropriate ways to solve them. He concludes that the basis of the management authority of the head of the educational institution will be the professional competence of the head of the educational institution, which will make it possible to make appropriate requirements for management activities. The concepts of "management competence of the head of an educational institution" and "professional competence of the head of an educational institution" can be considered as two different and interconnected concepts.

L.G. Kiseleva considers the management authority of the head of an educational institution to be a personal and professional feature in terms of a competency-based approach, including the willingness and ability to professionally perform management functions that should ensure effective solution of professional problems.[6] "Management Authority of the head of an educational institution" ability and readiness to perform management functions, but the authors call the composition of the functions different; on the general side, the result of performing these

functions should be an immersion in the tasks associated with the activity or development of an educational institution.

REFERENCES

1. Eugene YE.V. Socio-philosophical analysis of the development of Digital Culture in Uzbekistan. Doctor of philosophy in Philosophy (PhD) thesis abstract. Camarqand-2022. - p.19.
2. Yugai YE.V. Socio-philosophical analysis of the development of Digital Culture in Uzbekistan. Doctor of philosophy in Philosophy (PhD) thesis abstract. Camarqand-2022. - p.19.
3. Kapustin I. P., Tretyakov P. I., Shamova T. I. Management of educational systems // Moscow: Vldos. — 2002 — pp. 200-319.
4. Igropulo I.F. Methodology of development of the theory of management of innovative processes in an educational institution: dissertation ... Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. Stavropol, 2004. - 427 p.
5. Shamova T.I. Favorites / T. I. Shamova. - Moscow: Central Publishing House, 2004 (JSC Tip. News). - 320 p.
6. Kiseleva L.G. Formation of managerial competence of future specialists of preschool educational institutions: dissertation ... Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences. - Chita, 2007. - 249 p.